

Design and Analysis of Power Consumption of MPPT Controller in 130 nm CMOS Technology

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Abstract—This paper deals with design of a digital circuit for the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), especially analysis of its energy consumption. The circuit is based on a widely used direct tuning algorithm called Perturb & Observe (P&O). The digital circuit was designed at Register Transfer Level (RTL) using the descriptive language Verilog. The proposed digital circuit was synthesized in standard 130 nm CMOS technology, where also Place and Route (P&R) was performed.

Keywords—Energy Harvesters, Maximum Power Point Tracking, Perturb & Observe, MPPT algorithms

I. INTRODUCTION

Progressive development and research of semiconductor materials and technologies lead to improvement of their properties and reduction of transistor size. This inevitable process has direct impact on increasing integration density of electronic systems on a chip. With the shrinking of transistor dimensions, the power consumption is also reduced. This opens new possibilities for the design of low-power electronic systems, where the power consumption is the key parameter. Such systems are generally electronic circuits that do not have the ability to be connected to a permanent source of power. This category includes, for example, the progressive area Internet of Things (IoT) [?], where batteries are the most common source of energy. Modern designing techniques of low-power electronics open a straight way to the implementation of so-called energy harvesters (EH), which can extend the life of battery systems, or in some cases, completely replace them. Energy harvesters become an essential part of various electronic circuits, especially sensor systems [1].

This work presents digital MPPT controller for PWM/PFM regulator with P&O algorithm and analysis of its power consumption reduction. The paper is organized as follows: Section II discusses a basic structure of energy harvester systems. In Section III, the MPPT P&O algorithm is presented and main parts of the proposed controller are described. Section IV analyses power consumption of the MPPT controller, and Section V summarizes significant results obtained by simulations. The last Section concludes the paper.

II. ENERGY HARVESTERS

The function of EHs is to convert ambient energy (such as solar, thermal or mechanical) into the electricity. They are based on connection of an energy converter and a voltage converter. The two-part circuit is not able to operate efficiently due to input conditions fluctuations. In order to ensure efficient transmission of energy from the EH input to its output, it is necessary to connect additional tuning circuit. MPPT controller as the tuning circuit implemented in the EH is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Block diagram of an energy harvester.

The ability to tune the EH to the maximum energy transfer is made possible by indirect or direct tuning methods that differ in their complexity, speed or accuracy. These parameters most often negatively affect the size of necessary chip area and also the overall power consumption.

Connection of energy converters, such as piezoelectric or RF [3], with complex algorithms that are not optimized for power consumption can lead to a condition, where the value of power required for reliable operation of the system is close or even exceeds the value of power harvested by the EH. However, power consumption of MPPT controllers can be negligible to the energy generated by thermo-electric generators or solar cells. These EHs offer possibilities to create more robust tuning algorithms. It should also be noted that the energy harvester consists not only of a voltage converter and an MPPT controller but also other necessary blocks that also have certain power consumption.

All undesired properties significantly affect the overall efficiency of the energy harvester. Therefore, it is necessary to find a compromise between type of tuning methods, in particular, their complexity and tuning speed (together with a type of used energy harvester).

III. MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING

The EH, as the two-part circuit consisting of energy converter and voltage converter, is rarely able to ensure maximum energy transfer from its input to the output. MPPT algorithms help DC-DC converters compensate their input/output impedance mismatch. This is often done by driving signal, which can be Pulse-Width Modulated (PWM) or Pulse-Frequency Modulated (PFM). Fig. 2 depicts the block diagram of the proposed digital MPPT circuit.

Fig. 2: Block diagram of the proposed MPPT.

A. Tracking System

Fig. 3: MPP Tracker block.

For our design, we have chosen the most frequently used direct tuning method Perturb & Observe [2], [3]. The essence of this algorithm is the control of energy transfer through the EH that is based on the information about input power. This means that the voltage and current values must be measured and delivered to the MPP Tracker block, which is shown in Fig. 3. The absolute accuracy of the input values is not essential for this algorithm. The method evaluates magnitude of the change (of the measured input quantities) in the current step with respect to the previous measurement step.

In the beginning, algorithm itself reads the values of input voltage and current, and by multiplying them we obtain information about the input power in the current measurement step. In the following step, the

magnitude of changes in input power and voltage are determined. If the power change is equal to zero, the energy harvester is tuned to the his maximum transfer efficiency. Otherwise, it is necessary to evaluate the conditions for changes in the input voltage. The whole tuning process is described by flowchart depicted in Fig. 4. Evaluated conditions determine the relative

Fig. 4: Perturb & Observe algorithm flowchart.

position of the operating point in the power curve of a solar cell, and the displacement direction of this point with respect to the maximum power point (MPP). For a better idea of the operating point shift along the curve to the MPP, this process is illustrated in Fig. 5

Fig. 5: Operating point shifting to the MPP by P&O method.

B. PWM / PFM

The output stage of the MPPT block is modular. Pulse-Width Modulated or Pulse-Frequency Modulated signal can be implemented to drive a DC-DC converter. Both of modulation principles are based on the same type of inputs and output. Our design is primarily focused on a PWM generator. For this type of driving

signal, the rectangular shape with constant frequency and variable duty cycle is typical, as defined by Eq. 1.

$$DC = \left(\frac{T_{Log,1}}{T_{Log,1} + T_{Log,0}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

As one can observe in Fig. 6, m-bits width direct binary number as an input, it represents a reference value for generating the driving output signal. It is threshold, where the output signal is flipped from logical one (Log 1) to logical zero (Log 0). On the other hand, the flipping from Log 0 to Log 1 is caused by a counter overflow. The counter width is the same width

Fig. 6: PWM / PFM block.

as *Reference value*. The state of output signal depends on counter value and reference value. If the counter value is lower than the reference value, the output state will be Log 1. After evaluation of the opposite condition as true, the output signal state will be Log 0. As was mentioned above, the reset state of Log 1 ensures counter overflow. This finally causes that frequency of the output signal is constant and the duty cycle can vary by the reference value. A more detailed description of PWM generator represents the flowchart shown in Fig. 7

Fig. 7: Flowchart of generating Pulse-Width Modulated driving signal.

IV. POWER CONSUMPTION ANALYSIS OF MPPT CONTROLLER

The MPPT controller is a sequential synchronous digital circuit that needs clock signal to function. Its power consumption is not negligible, especially for harvested energy with low energy density. In digital circuits, power consumption consists of static and dynamic portions, as it is expressed by equation Eq. 2.

$$P = P_s + P_d \quad (2)$$

The value of static consumption P_s is mostly given by the number of logic gates, multiplexers, flip-flops and ambient temperature. Dynamic consumption P_d represents a much larger contribution to the total energy consumption P , as expressed by equation Eq. 3:

$$P_d = \alpha C_L V^2 f_{clk} \quad (3)$$

Load capacity C_L , supply voltage V and clock frequency f_{clk} in equation Eq. 3 are in the vast majority of cases static parameters that cannot be changed dynamically. The coefficient α is function of the whole system, which expresses the probability of logic state change for the given node from Log 1 to Log 0 or vice versa. For example, in case of the logic inverter consisting of PMOS and NMOS transistors in the common output node, this probability is 0.5 [4]. Schematic of an inverter in CMOS technology is depicted in Fig. 8. In logic circuits based on CMOS technology,

Fig. 8: Transistor level of a logic inverter.

in a static state, at least one type of transistors is always closed what is also demonstrated by the logic inverter shown in Fig. 8. If the input is in Log 1, the PMOS transistor will be closed and the output will be connected to the lowest potential via opened NMOS transistor. Otherwise, if the input is in Log 0, the NMOS transistor will be closed and the PMOS brings the highest voltage potential to the output. In neither case, the highest and lowest potentials are short-circuited, so the static power consumption is very close to zero.

However, the transient state of the inverter's transmission characteristic is critical, when at one moment, both types of transistors are opened and a conductive channel is created between the power supply V_{DD} and the ground GND [5]. Therefore, In CMOS logic circuits, the highest power consumption is in transient state when a short-circuit current flows through the circuit for a short time, what is depicted in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9: I-V and Transfer characteristics of inverter.

Fig. 10: Clock gating cell schematic.

In order to reduce the dynamic power consumption P_d , it is necessary to avoid excessive and especially unnecessary switching of logic levels. In case of sequential circuits containing flip-flops, it is necessary to avoid excessive activity. The most dominant technique for controlling the distribution of the clock signal to the flip-flops is *Clock Gating* [6], which prevents an unnecessary and unwanted clock signal to the registers when there is no change in the input data.

V. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The MPPT controller was designed at a higher abstraction level, specifically at RTL using the Verilog hardware description language. It was synthesized into a standard 130 nm CMOS technology using Cadence environment. The time criteria for synthesis are given in TABLE I. The proposed digital circuit based on

TABLE I: MPPT circuit synthesis parameters.

Parameters	Value
Clock period [ns]	5
Rising edge time [ps]	250
Falling edge time [ps]	250
Jitter [ps]	70

the basic P&O algorithm consists of 750 standard cells, which occupy $10\,964\ \mu\text{m}^2$ of the chip area. Synthesized digital circuit was imported into the analog environment of Cadence to achieve the most accurate simulation results. Supply voltage V_{DD} is the most dominant parameter within the reduction of the total consumption because the power consumption decreases by the square of supply voltage. With the focus on this parameter, we investigated the total average power consumption at $V_{DD} = 1.2\ \text{V}$ and $V_{DD} = 0.4\ \text{V}$ in different corner conditions of the fabrication process and with changes in ambient temperature. The achieved simulation results are summarized in TABLE II.

TABLE II: MPPT power consumption under different corner conditions and ambient temperature.

P [$\mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$]	$V_{DD} = 1,2\ \text{V}$			$V_{DD} = 0,4\ \text{V}$		
	SS	TT	FF	SS	TT	FF
T = -20 °C	-	2.67	-	0.04	0.05	0.12
T = 27 °C	-	7.40	-	0.05	0.17	0.71
T = 85 °C	-	35.85	-	0.19	1.09	4.25

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, design of a MPPT controller and its power consumption analysis, as an important part of a EH, were presented. Through a general analysis of digital circuits, we have found out several ways to reduce the power consumption to minimum. From among the analyzed techniques, reducing the supply voltage value has been proven to be the most effective way to reduce the power consumption. The total circuit consumption ($P_s + P_d$) was simulated in all fabrication process corners and temperatures at $V_{DD} = 1.2\ \text{V}$ and $V_{DD} = 0.4\ \text{V}$. The obtained simulation results are depicted in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12. Reducing the V_{DD}

Fig. 11: Power consumption as a function of V_{DD} under nominal conditions.

Fig. 12: Power consumption as a function of temperature for lowered value of V_{DD} .

value to $0.4\ \text{V}$ in typical corner and different temperature conditions have decreased the power consumption to $P_{avg} = 0.173\ \mu\text{W}/\text{MHz}$. This result is almost 43-times reduction in power consumption compared to the case of $V_{DD} = 1.2\ \text{V}$ under the same conditions.

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